

EXPLORING THE EXPERIENCES, SATISFACTORY LEVEL, AND VIEWS OF DEPED MODULE WRITERS ON THE MODULE WRITING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess as to what the experiences of teachers are with regards to the implementation of writing modules, to see the satisfactory level among module writers during the implementation of the said modality, and to identify the qualitative views of module writers in terms of the development made by the Department of Education. This research used a mixed method in gathering data (quantitative and qualitative). The research used descriptive research design through a survey-questionnaire. The total number of respondents is 38. Weighted mean was used to measure the experiences and satisfactory level of module writers during the implementation of writing modules and to the recent developments by the Department of Education. Thematic was used as well in analyzing the data from the open-ended question. The following aspects got a *Very High* competence equivalence *writing process, assurance for quality modules, need for internet connectivity, and risk upon the writing process*. The competence equivalence for the satisfactory level of module writers towards the development by the Department of Education is *High*. The views of the module writers are as follows: the Vision, Mission and Goals of the Department of Education are still on its pedestal amid this pandemic; pieces of training for development are necessary for module writers; flexibility with the new modality is a challenge to educators; *digitization* of modules is a development in the ends of the teachers; and, the Department of Education is doing its part to satisfy the needs of teachers.

Keywords: *module writing, teacher experiences, module implementation, satisfactory level, challenges in module development, digitization of learning modules*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education - as one of the trifocal agencies assigned for education in the Philippines, certainly assured that schooling should continue within the School Year 2020-2021, amid the pandemic, thus, a wide consultation was being done. In a survey conducted by the said department of 700,000 participants, the majority said that they wanted to go to school amid this crisis. The said system made a committee to see the curriculum and the competencies per subject area to have a lesser number of competencies compared before, thus, the birth of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (*MELCs*) (Oplan Balik-Eskwela – Brigada Eskwela, 2020).

In suspension of the first announcement by the department that the School Year 2020-2021 will start by August 24, 2020, a memorandum from the Office of the President (2020), stated that it should be done by October 5, 2020, so that the Department of Education will have enough time as to the preparations of the new learning modalities for a smooth School Year. Considering the health risks of the students, in a Department Memorandum 32 (2020), it was emphasized that teachers and students will not cater to the *face-to-face* modality of learning. The Learning Continuity Plan regards those students who will be using different learning modalities to cater for the *MELCs* - the *online learning*, televisions and local radio stations, and self-learning modules. The usage of these modalities might be suspended once everything gets back to normal.

Since the Regional and Division offices must decide as to what modality it will be using for the new normal, in the context of Division of Negros Oriental of Region VII, it was decided that it will be using the modular approach. Teachers, as *curricularists*, are the ones assigned for the writing and implementation of the said modules. Due to the issues raised by different organizations, such as the erroneous content of some modules, taking risks among teachers amid the pandemic, and the connectivity difficulties among teachers in attending *webinars*, this study aims to assess as to what the experiences of teachers are with regards to the implementation of writing modules. It also aims to see the satisfactory level among module writers during the implementation of the said modality. Lastly, the research is concerned as well on the qualitative views of module writers in terms of the development made by the Department of Education.

Research Questions

The study is designed to assess the implementation of writing modules for the modular approach. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the different experiences of teachers / module writers during the implementation of it as to the following aspects:
 - 1.1 writing process;
 - 1.2 assurance for quality modules;
 - 1.3 need for internet connectivity; and,
 - 1.4 risk upon the writing process?

2. What is the satisfactory level of teachers in terms of the development made by the Department of Education towards the implementation of the module writing for modular approach?
3. In general, what are your views with regards to DepEd's recent developments? How can you say that it is doing its best to serve its employees?

METHODOLOGY

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 38 module writers from the selected elementary and secondary schools of the Municipality of Siaton who were chosen using purposive-random sampling. These teachers came from Felipe Tayko Memorial School, Maloh Central School, Siaton National High School, Siaton Science High School, and Sumaliring High School. These teachers were the ones stipulated in the memorandum who were assigned to write modules based on the competencies assigned to them. They came from different subject areas. Purposive-random sampling was used since the researcher would like to focus on the characteristics of the population. Shown below is the distribution of the teachers by the set of subject areas stipulated by DepEd Order No. 8, Series of 2015:

Set of Subjects	Number of Module Writers
Languages / ESP / AralPan	24
Math / Science	7
MAPEH / TLE	7
Total	38

This research used a mixed method in gathering data (quantitative and qualitative). The research used a descriptive research design. The main source of data was through a survey-questionnaire. This was used to determine the experiences of module writers during the implementation of module writing and their satisfactory level, and to the developments made by the Department of Education as well as their ends towards the recent developments by the system. The data gathered were analyzed and were given several interpretations based on the pieces of experience and satisfactory level. These are bases for the assessment of the implementation of module writing.

The Municipality of Siaton is located at the Southern part of Negros Oriental. It is divided into four districts and is under the Division of Negros Oriental for the Department of Education. Felipe Tayko Memorial School is the central elementary school for Siaton II District; while on the other hand, Maloh Central School is the center for Siaton III. The two are public elementary schools. Siaton National High School is the implementing high school of the Municipality of Siaton under Siaton II District of the Division of Negros Oriental. The said school offers basic schooling from Grade 7 to Grade 12 and has its annexes – two of them are Siaton Science High School of Siaton III District and Sumaliring High School from Siaton I.

Selected teachers from the said schools were chosen as module writers in preparation for the modular approach as a modality that aroused during the pandemic. Having the views and assessments of these teachers during the implementation of module writing and their satisfaction level of the developments by the Department of Education were helpful in attaining the objectives of the study.

Data Gathering Instruments & Procedures

To gather the important data, the researcher used survey-questionnaire. For easy access to the respondents, the researcher used the *Google Forms* feature and formulated the survey. In the first part, the researcher presented his letter of intent to conduct the research. After the agreement from the respondent, basic pieces of information were asked such as the name of the respondent (which is optional), and the subject taught by the said teacher based on the classification given. In the second part, module writers were given time to assess their experiences based on the aspects given in the Statement of the Problem. There were four indicators in each aspect designed by the researcher. In the third part, module writers were to answer as to their satisfactory level on the recent development of the Department of Education. Before submitting, a divergent question regarding the views of every module writer to DepEd's recent developments was asked to gather qualitative data.

The highly proficient colleagues of the researcher were considered as *external experts* to see the validity of the said survey-questionnaire. Suggestions and other comments were incorporated for the betterment of the survey. The link of the survey was disseminated through *Messenger*, and their approval in participating in the survey was considered.

Ethical considerations were made – confidentiality and anonymity among respondents. In the end, the researcher consolidated all the responses using the platform used by downloading the responses in general. Analyses and interpretation of data were done after having the responses.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tool is used in the conduct of the research:

Weighted Mean. Used to measure the experiences and satisfactory level of module writers during the implementation of writing modules and to the recent developments by the Department of Education. The interpretation below was used (Statistical Correlation, 2009):

Score	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent	Scale	Explanation
7	Strongly Agree	Very High	6.15 – 7.00	The experience manifested by the module writers 87% -100% of the time.
6	Agree	High	5.29 – 6.14	The experience manifested by the module writers 73% - 86% of the time.
5	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat High	4.43 – 5.28	The experience manifested by the module writers 59% - 72% of the time.
4	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate	3.57 – 4.42	The experience manifested by the module writers 43% - 58% of the time.
3	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Low	2.71 – 3.56	The experience manifested by the module writers 29% -42% of the time.
2	Disagree	Low	1.85 – 2.70	The experience manifested by the module writers 15% - 28% of the time.
1	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	1.00 – 1.84	The experience manifested by the module writers 1% - 14% of the time or below.

Scope and Limitation

The study was focused on the assessment of the implementation of module writing for the modular approach in time of pandemic; thus, the experiences of teachers were considered. The teachers' satisfactory level regarding the development made by the Department of Education as to the implementation done was also part of its scope. The respondents were teachers who are module writers from selected elementary and secondary schools in the Municipality of Siaton teaching different subjects and grade levels. The study was also focused on the views of teachers towards the development made by the Department of Education recently.

Limitations of the study are as follows: Although the researcher tried his best to motivate the respondents to answer honestly, other factors, which are out of his control like the physical and emotional conditions of module writers towards the survey, will be set as limitations. The different subject areas taught by the teachers might have also affected their responses, therefore counted as one. Also, the study was limited to teachers from Siaton only due to time-constraint and to limit the interaction as a mandate from the set of health protocols as far as the pandemic was concerned. The testing of reliability of the questionnaire was also set for its limitations due to time-constraints.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part contains the data gathered in the research arranged specifically based on the statement of the problem. Results were presented in a tabular manner and were discussed textually.

Table 1.1

Experiences of Module Writers in the Aspect Writing Process (n=38)

<i>During the implementation of writing modules, I was...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
1. Honored that my written modules were published and used by the students within the Division of Negros Oriental.	6.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Fortunate since I was chosen to write modules based on the topic/s or competencies stipulated from the memorandum.	6.61	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Amazed since I was able to collaborate with my other co-writers via limited <i>face-to-face</i> or virtual.	6.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Privileged that the Department of Education equipped me with the necessary skills and competencies about module writing that gave me the ease of doing such.	6.42	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	6.53	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.29 – 6.14	Agree	High
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat High
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Low
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.1 shows the experiences of module writers in the aspect *writing process*. All the indicators get a verbal description of *Strongly Agree* with a *Very High* competence equivalent.

The results imply that module writers are honored since their modules were used by the students within the whole Division of Negros Oriental. They were also glad after having been selected as writers as stipulated in the memorandum and were able to collaborate with the other writers in different ways. These act as fulfillment in the ends of the module writers. They were also privileged that the Department of Education has equipped them with the necessary skills and competencies towards module writing. In general, the composite $w\bar{x}$ is 6.53 that is equivalent to a *Very High* competence.

These experiences are in relation as to what Sec. Briones foreseen – those teachers are gathered and share their experiences and expertise in general to create modules for the new modality (Malipot, 2020b). The collaboration of teachers plays an important role in a certain educational system. There is a need for every individual to cooperate for the attainment of the Vision, Mission, and Goals of the system. In a study by Ostovar-Nameghi and Sheikahmadi (2016), it has pointed out that in professional development in the education sector, collaboration among teachers, who in the context of the study are module writers, is an efficient mode for the attainment.

In implication, collaboration among teachers should be enriched within the Department of Education. Pieces of training towards the advancement of the curriculum should also be considered to attain the Vision, Mission, and Goals of the Department of Education.

Table 1.2
Experiences of Module Writers in the Aspect Assurance for Quality Modules (n=38)

<i>During the implementation of writing modules, I was...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
1. Glad that revisions were made to make the modules more aligned with the necessary competencies, and in general made it finer until the last look.	6.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Not hesitant to submit my work to the <i>Quality Assurance Team (QAT)</i> to see the content, grammar, coherence, lay-outing, and other related undertakings.	6.45	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Able to seek advice from the <i>QAT</i> as far as module writing is concerned, may it be in person or virtual.	6.42	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Able to reflect that after the students have answered the modules, there is a need for revision and reconsideration for another cycle towards quality assurance.	6.21	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	6.39	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.29 – 6.14	Agree	High
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat High
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Low
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.2 shows the experiences of module writers in the aspect *assurance for quality modules*. All the indicators get a verbal description of *Strongly Agree* with a *Very High* competence equivalent.

The results imply that module writers are glad that several revisions of their written modules were incorporated after submitting their works to the *Quality Assurance Team (QAT)*. The QAT was also responsible enough for advising the writers. On the other hand, module writers, who are also teachers, believed that another series of revisions and reconsideration towards quality assurance should be done since learning materials are obsolete – changes as time goes on. In general, the composite wx is 6.39 that is equivalent to a *Very High* competence.

The necessity for the modules to undergo quality assurance is an important aspect in the writing process of modules. This has been raised by Hamweete (2012), that in the data collected from 1,107 students who are enrolled using distance education, students were not satisfied with the quality of modules given to them. They indicated that these learning materials were less interactive, the usage of language is not appropriate to the level of the learners, and the font sizes and types were not in line with the learning materials used. It was concluded that there is a need for quality assurance for the learning materials before using those for the teaching-and-learning process, thus requires pieces of training to writers and editors.

In the context of the Division of Negros Oriental, revisions of the self-learning modules are already made by individuals stipulated as editors in the memorandum. This manpower training is a mile towards the advancement and finer ways in hitting the *MELCs*.

Table 1.3
Experiences of Module Writers in the Need for Internet Connectivity (n=38)

<i>During the implementation of writing modules, I was...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
1. Able to see the importance of having internet connectivity especially when browsing important information, facts, and data to be included in the content during module writing as references.	6.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Able to see the importance of having internet connectivity, especially when announcements and other whereabouts of module writing are raised in <i>group chats</i> and other online platforms.	6.66	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Able to see the importance of having internet connectivity especially when attending <i>webinars</i> to make me more equipped towards the new modality of teaching.	6.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Able to maximize my technological skills to adapt to the <i>new normal</i> and especially during the module writing process.	6.5	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.29 – 6.14	Agree	High
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat High
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Low
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.3 shows the experiences of module writers in the aspect *need for internet connectivity*. All the indicators get a verbal description of *Strongly Agree* with a *Very High* competence equivalent.

The results imply that module writers strongly agree that internet connectivity is really a need for browsing information that will be added to the content of the modules. This connection is also a necessity for having some updates among focal persons since announcements are raised in online platforms such as *group chats* of *Messenger*, and for attending *webinars* regarding the new modality of teaching. Truly, module writers have maximized their technological skills to adapt to the *new normal*. In general, the composite $w\bar{x}$ is 6.62 that is equivalent to a *Very High* competence.

It is an inevitable fact that the internet is the main source of information nowadays, thus we cannot hold that module writers, in the context of the study, strongly agree that having connectivity is a necessity towards easy implementation of writing modules. In addition, in a study conducted by the Pew Research Center (n.d.), the internet has been the prime source of information all around the globe and has already surpassed newspapers as a source of national and international news. Aside from having this as a source of information, the internet is also important to teachers, especially in attending *webinars*. According to Mohalik and Poddar (2020), teachers make some extra effort to make themselves updated by participating in different *webinars* available for them depending on their needs and interests to adapt to the *new normal* in education. Aside from that, even if the problem of connectivity is a big challenge among educators because of their geographical locations, still, they manage to find ways.

As of July 2021, the distribution of the connectivity allowance is on-going not only to the teaching personnel but at the same time to the non-teaching personnel.

Table 1.4

Experiences of Module Writers in the Aspect Risk Upon the Writing Process (n=38)

<i>During the implementation of writing modules, I was...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
1. Blessed since I was not infected with CoViD-19 during the times when I wrote the modules assigned to me.	6.76	Strongly Agree	Very High

2. Able to contemplate that I as a teacher is a hero in this time of pandemic after sacrificing a lot that may include the risk of my well-being.	6.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Feeling safe since during the module writing, there have been minimal interactions towards my co-writers because aside from the traditional <i>face-to-face</i> , other means such as the use of technology have been monopolized (e.g., <i>group chat</i> , <i>e-mail</i> , <i>etc.</i>).	6.39	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Able to accomplish the modules as per instruction without feeling risky at all (e.g., going to someone/ somewhere else to ask some advice or connect to the internet).	6.39	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	6.56	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.29 – 6.14	Agree	High
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat High
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Low
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.4 shows the experiences of module writers in the aspect of *risk upon the writing process*. All the indicators get a verbal description of *Strongly Agree* with a *Very High* competence equivalent.

The results imply that module writers strongly agree that they were blessed not to be infected with CoViD-19 during the implementation of the module writing; thus, consider themselves as front lines towards sacrifice for better learning among students. Other means, aside from the traditional *face-to-face* were being used. They also strongly agree that they do not feel risky at all, especially when asking someone for help during the writing process. In general, the composite *wx* is 6.56 that is equivalent to a *Very High* competence.

To sum up, from the indicators above, teachers are prime movers in the academe, especially in these trying times because of the pandemic. Even if teachers are risking themselves for the educational commitment, “*but in no way did it hinder the unyielding commitment and drive of those at the front lines of education – Filipino teachers.*” Even if teachers find a hard time facing numerous challenges towards the implementation of the writing of modules, numerous Filipino teachers remain “passionate” to provide quality education among their clientele (Business Mirror, 2020).

The DepEd is also pushing its employees to have themselves vaccinated. The principals were then asked to enlist the faculty and staff who are not yet vaccinated. This

development can be beneficial to reduce the risks of teaching and non-teaching personnel to CoViD-19.

Table 1.5
Summary Table of the Experiences of Module Writers in the Different Aspects (n=38)

Aspect	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
1. Writing Process	6.53	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Assurance for Quality Modules	6.39	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Need for Internet Connectivity	6.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Risk Upon the Writing Process	6.56	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.29 – 6.14	Agree	High
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat High
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Low
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.5 shows the summary table of the experiences of module writers in different aspects. All the aspects get a verbal description of *Strongly Agree* with a *Very High* competence equivalent. The following aspects are as follows with their respective $w\bar{x}$: *writing process* ($w\bar{x} = 6.53$); *assurance for quality modules* ($w\bar{x} = 6.39$); *need for internet connectivity* ($w\bar{x} = 6.62$); and *risk upon the writing process* ($w\bar{x} = 6.56$).

These four aspects, having similar results, testify that there are varied experiences among teachers during the implementation of module writing during the modular approach.

Table 2
Satisfactory Level of Teachers in Terms of the Recent Developments by the Department of Education (n=38)

<i>During the implementation of writing modules, I was...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
1. The Department of Education has equipped me more with pieces of training (e.g., INSET, webinars, etc.) and the Division of Negros Oriental paves its way for the <i>digitization</i> of modules to aid learning in case there is no formal <i>face-to-face</i> classes yet.	6.37	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. The system is trying to issue an immediate rectification vis-à-vis the errors found in modules as reported in different means and promises more	6.18	Strongly Agree	Very High

quality assured materials by having “specialists” on it.			
3. There is an increase of 1,500 for the Cash Allowance among teachers since the department believes that being a teacher amid this pandemic might put an individual at risk.	5.95	Agree	High
4. The Connectivity Allowance was given by the department since it has seen the importance of having connection anent this new normal.	5.86	Agree	High
Composite	6.09	Agree	High

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Competence Equivalent
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.29 – 6.14	Agree	High
4.43 – 5.28	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat High
3.57 – 4.42	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
2.71 – 3.56	Somewhat Disagree	Somewhat Low
1.85 – 2.70	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.84	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2 shows the satisfactory level of teachers / module writers in terms of the recent developments by the Department of Education.

The first two indicators get a verbal description of *Strongly Agree* with a *Very High* competence equivalent. The results imply that module writers strongly agree that the Department of Education’s move towards the *digitization* of modules and for the immediate ratification of the erroneous content of the modules were considerably developments. The third and fourth indicators get a verbal description of *Agree* with a *High* competence equivalent. This implies that module writers are considering the allowances such as the Connectivity Allowance and the increase for Cash Allowance as developments anent to their sacrifices done during this time of pandemic. In general, the composite wx is 6.09 that is equivalent to a *High* competence.

In consideration of the students’ health risks, in a Department Memorandum 32 (2020), it was emphasized that teachers and students will not cater to the *face-to-face* modality of learning. The Learning Continuity Plan, as proposed by the Department of Education, regards those students who will be using different learning modalities to cater for the *MELCs* such as *online learning*, through televisions and local radio stations, and through self-learning modules. The usage of these modules “*might be suspended once everything gets back to normal.*” In the context of the Division of Negros Oriental, after the clamors of the modular teaching, the division developed the program of *digitization* of the modules by supplementing videos related to these modules. This act by the Department is considered as a development for the aspect of the *writing process*.

For the *quality assurance* aspect, module writers strongly agree that the stand of the Department of Education about the errors made by the teachers is considerably a development towards it. The DepEd Undersecretary for Curriculum and Implementation Division San Antonio highlighted that “*content errors found inappropriate shall be rectified*”

via an issuance from the concerned Regional Director if the SLM is used in the whole region.” The system also appeals for public understanding after these module errors and asks for humane considerations (Malipot, 2020a).

Module writers agree that the ways the Department of Education is doing right now – justifying the needs of teachers for connection through appropriating funds from the National Government for connectivity load allowance (Quevedo, 2021), and adding a 1,500 pesos from the 3,500-peso cash allowance intended for the purchase of tangible and intangible teaching supplies and materials, for the conduct of various modes of learning, internet, and other communication expenses, and for annual medical examination expenses (DepEd.gov, 2021) – are considered developments at their ends for the aspects *need for internet connectivity* and *risk upon the writing process* respectively.

In general, the module writers agree that developments are being made by the Department of Education to suffice the needs of teachers amid these trying times into the different aspects. These developments should be maintained and maybe enriched by the Department of Education as time goes by depending on the arousal of needs and interests of the teachers.

Table 3

Views of the Module Writers Towards DepEd’s Recent Developments (n=38)

During the recent developments, I have these following sentiments...

1. *DepEd is the most challenged department in this time of pandemic. The DepEd's primary goal, "No one should be left behind" is positively progressing.*
 2. *I know that the department is also having hard times in pursuing improvements and developments just to cater the welfare of its employees. But that does not mean we cannot work it out since the passion itself is there to make sure that there will be no students left behind.*
 3. *The DepEd has given its best by all means just to achieve its mission and vision.*
 4. *In spite this pandemic, the Department of Education is good enough to find ways to solve the problem when it comes to the quality of education students deserved. Perhaps, I still consider them blessed to continue their education with the use of modules prepared by teachers. Nowadays, it is very vital to use the modules as the mode of delivery for learnings among students since face-to-face classes is still not allowed.*
 5. *The institution has started the fundamental steps towards modular learning, while issues have slowly aroused. It was worthy to note that it was addressed. However, programs such as cash allowance was neither given voluntarily or at the expense of passing requirements. It must be hassle free.*
 6. *Continue developing for the better amidst this pandemic.*
 7. *Struggling*
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8. *Department of education really worked hard for the good of our Filipino learners. The department also is doing its best to cope on teacher's needs. Congrats to the department.*
 9. *Give the module writer as well as the QA enough time.*
 10. *Financial stability despite pandemic*
 11. *The department is doubling efforts to continue education despite the pandemic. I applaud with high salute to the secretary for this decision. As a module writer with 30 authentic works, I find this school year very challenging, but we can do it. I will continue to share and make modules as instructed to for our future Negrense leaders.*
 12. *Having these developments especially in this time of pandemic can be said to be very relevant to address the needs for continuous education.*
 13. *In amid of pandemic, I am very lucky because I was given an opportunity to develop my skill as writer and a member of the QA team and at the same time, the government has continue to provide monthly salary and incentives*
 14. *The recent development is appropriate for the learning modality needed by learners nowadays. The action taken by DepEd is very commendable.*
 15. *DepEd is doing its best to deliver education to our school children despite this pandemic. DepEd Division of Negros Oriental are now on its way to digitization of the crafted modules. The division is now creating a lot of innovations to deliver basic education right at the learner's doorstep, making learning easy and convenient to them.*
 16. *I'm so happy because despite this pandemic our department made a great job to reach our children through modules and I am so privilege and honored because I am one of the module writers.*
 17. *By giving them the funds that they need.*
 18. *I can say that DepEd really provides trainings and seminars for its employees so they can address the needs of learners.*
 19. *DepEd has fulfilled its mission and vision even during pandemic*
 20. *The department support us in many ways, and it is very much appreciated.*
 21. *With the DepEd's recent developments, I can say that they motivate employees by giving them the opportunities to position themselves as subject matter experts. Also by giving them high profile growth opportunities that will make them feel valued and appreciated. Lastly, by inspiring employees to work harder to reach the department's goal.*
 22. *The DepEd is doing their best to serve the students and the parents.*
 23. *Excellent*
 24. *No comment at all*
 25. *Well though there are lapses, still the department has done their very best to help the teachers in order for them to facilitate the learning effectively.*
 26. *No comment at all*
 27. *There is no perfect system. DepEd is doing its best to serve the teachers. The recent developments are really fascinating in our ends.*
 28. *The Department of Education is trying to provide teachers needs in order to function well specially in the completion of the task given during the pandemic*
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time specifically writing of modules to meet the need of the students. Education must continue.

29. *They have to give enough budget for internet connection because not all module writers were able to receive yet the 1, 500 allowances for the internet connection. They required to have a receipt of your internet connection before they give 1,500. In my case I was able to receive it.*
30. *Div. of Neg.Or sometimes rejected the health protocols. Supervisors still gave advised to the writers to have a face-to-face QA conducted at some private rented hall that made other teachers infected and suffered from COVID19.*
31. *The Department of Education is doing their part in order to continue to cater the necessary learning to the learner in spite of the pandemic. Using modular approach make the learning continue, the teachers still play the vital part in molding the youth to be educationally equipped in order for them to be globally competitive.*
32. *DepEd is trying its best to improve the delivery of quality education to its learners however the writers are not given incentives or allowance for the additional work that was given to them.*
33. *This recent development serves the employees best as still performing our duties to the best of our ability and also a way of helping the government in the fighting covid-19 in this time of pandemic.*
34. *The Department is really trying to find ways to continue learning/education amidst this pandemic.*
35. *They are always finding ways to improve the teaching and learning process amidst the pandemic.*
36. *DepEd is not selfish they really think what is best for all.*
37. *The Department of Education continuously ensures equal access to education through different teaching modalities (e.g., modular print) to cater the educational needs of students despite the COVID-19 pandemic. - DepEd equips its employees with different trainings/workshops for professional development, provides opportunities to be part of the conceptualization of modules and other learning materials, and provides benefits and compensation to its employees.*
38. *The Department do all the things needed by the teachers and learners to achieve highest possible improvement to ensure and enabling and supportive environment for effective learning to happen.*

Table 3 shows the views of module writers towards DepEd's recent developments, especially in these times of crisis and what are the ways the system does to serve the best for teachers. To sum it up, the responses of module writers are as follows (in general):

(a) The attainment of the Vision, Mission, and Goals amid this pandemic has continued thus, development towards quality education has been pointed out. In a survey conducted by UNESCO, as cited by DepEd Commons (2020), 87% of the population of the students have been affected due to CoViD-19. Most of those affected came from the marginalized sectors. Also, the agency highlighted that *"Education cannot*

wait. If learning stops, we will lose human capital.”; thus, the pandemic should not be a hindrance to continue learning and achieving the Vision, Mission, and Goals of the Department of Education.

The Department of Education, as the focal agency for basic schooling, continually promotes “*quality basic education*” towards its clientele (DepEd Mission). It is also mandated in Article XIV, Section 1 of the Philippine Constitution (1987), that “*The State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.*”

(b) Pieces of training for development with regards to module writing are necessary for them which the system is encouraging. Pieces of training for module writing are necessary for teachers, thus implementing one can be very helpful to teachers to design their modules of clarity and quality. To cite again, in data collected from 1,107 students who are enrolled using distance education, students were not satisfied with the quality of modules given to them. They indicated that these learning materials were less interactive due to the use of language and fonts. It was concluded that there is a need for quality assurance for the learning materials before using those for the teaching-and-learning process, thus, requires training to writers and editors (Hamweete, 2012).

(c) Flexibility such as the implementation of “No Child Left Behind” for the new modality is a challenge among teachers, students, and parents thru adapting it. It is a challenge among different individuals to adapt with the new modality at the same time implementing the “*No Child Left Behind*” Policy of the Department of Education. Teachers, as the frontiers of this matter, should be flexible enough by giving interventions to students who have deficiencies in *MELCs*. As highlighted by Magsambol (2020), teachers should give “reasonable” number of tasks to students to prevent burnout.

(d) The recent digitization of modules can be considered as developments to address the needs and interests of the learners. The Division of Negros Oriental, after the clamors of the modular teaching, developed the program of *digitization* of the modules by supplementing videos related to these modules in all subjects. This is a development in the ends of the teachers that can aid them towards the understanding of students in lessons found in modules. According to Gadayan (2021), this act of the Department of Education can be considered as a milestone towards a better understanding of students if ever the modular approach is still used for the next School Year. This can really be advantageous in making students more knowledgeable even if they are at a distance from their teacher.

(e) The Department of Education is doing its part to satisfy the needs of teachers specifically financial stability among teachers amid this pandemic. Coping with these needs are considerable developments. Majority of teachers believe that there is no perfect system. It is undeniably true that there are factors that DepEd is trying to develop especially in terms of development and manpower training. However, teachers, in their ends continue to believe that time will come, the system will be finer for development and manpower training, thus, patience is the main key for it. As

of now, teachers are satisfied with what the system is trying to suffice based on their needs.

To put into context the results in the development and manpower training dimensions, since the Department of Education continuously aims for the attainment of the Vision, Mission, and Goals of it, the system should fully-develop its employees since they are the “true assets of an organization.” Also, pieces of training in which teachers can really have a full grasp on the totality towards the teaching-and-learning process, not only regarding the implementation of module writing, should be emphasized. If possible, teachers and non-teaching personnel should indulge themselves in seeking higher education to make themselves globally competitive and to meet the standards towards professional development.

Aside from these, the Department of Education should also promote teachers to devise strategic intervention materials to the least learned competencies through a series of workshops by the department in to address the needs of the clientele to sustain the “*No Child Left Behind Policy*”. Experts regarding this matter should be considered as “specialists” and must supervise towards the process of making these intervention materials.

In addition, the Department should also look upon other modalities and develop those to cater for other students. Since distance learning is already used, it might be possible to upgrade other ways such as blended learning, or the use of asynchronous and synchronous way of teaching. In general, to cater the satisfaction of employees towards development, the Department of Education should advocate ways leading development and manpower training.

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. The following aspects got a *Very High* competence equivalence *writing process*, *assurance for quality modules*, *need for internet connectivity*, and *risk upon the writing process*.
2. The competence equivalence for the satisfactory level of module writers towards the development by the Department of Education is *High*.
3. The views of the module writers are as follows: the Vision, Mission and Goals of the Department of Education are still on its pedestal amid this pandemic; pieces of training for development are necessary for module writers; flexibility with the new modality is a challenge to educators; *digitization* of modules is a development in the ends of the teachers; and, the Department of Education is doing its part to satisfy the needs of teachers.

In general, module writers believe that the Department of Education is doing its best to meet the developments and the required manpower training for the teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions given, the researcher recommends the following:

Teachers / Module Writers. Even if there are some instances in the field that are quite beyond the control and exigency of anybody, teachers and module writers should be capable enough to become managers of time and flexible enough so that they can serve what is best for the learners. Module writers should also take time to exert means such as attending *webinars* outside DepEd to have varied experiences and levels of expertise in module writing. On the other hand, if ever there are instances that the teachers' lives are put at risk, they should air their sentiments to their direct superiors especially with regards to the new modality.

Students, Parents, and Community. As clientele, students should also air their sentiments to teachers in a form of communication with regards to the attainment of the *MELCs* whether they have difficulties with it. Parents and the community, as stakeholders, should also take part in airing and filling up these deficiencies for the system to design specific plans of action depending on the needs to be filled. This communication can really be helpful to teachers for them to design intervention materials for the competencies least learned by students.

Department of Education. As the main system in-charge, the Department of Education should enrich more development and manpower training among their teachers, especially for the implementation of module writing as a supplementary to the modular approach. By identifying the needs of the teachers, may it be by conducting a survey, it can really be helpful to the system to cater to those needs and can be bases towards craftsmanship of the human development plan. There should be two-way communication between the Department of Education as well as with the teachers on it.

Further Researchers. This research can help other researchers to see the other variables that were not given much emphasis during the conduct of this research such as the efficiency of the use of the modular approach in learning by the Department of Education and at the same time the ends of DepEd towards its plans for development and manpower training for teachers. Other challenges faced by teachers such as the interventions they have done can also be taken into consideration. Moreover, the effectiveness of the *digitization* project can also be a good point to look upon.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All the respondents were given informed consent before the conduct of the research. They were informed as to what are the important data to be gathered from them as well as the ways in which the research will be conducted. They were free to withdraw anytime during the conduct of the research without consequences. There was no disruption of classes in the conduct of the said research.

Ethical considerations were considered during the conduct of the study. Confidentiality and anonymity among respondents were being assured. Data storage measures were through Google Drive, in which only the researcher can access, considering that the data needed has a bearing on the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Lastly, the researcher assured the welfare of the respondents will be free from harm. All raw data were deleted from Google Drive, and all data gathered from them were disposed of after the conduct of the research since all the data were solely for educational purposes. Plagiarism was highly discouraged in the conduct of the research.

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